

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TASK BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING IN
ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING FOR 2nd SEMESTER OF
ACCOUNTING STUDENTS STATE POLYTECHNIC OF
MANADO, INDONESIA**

**Rolina Emmy Manggopa¹ⁱ,
Selvie Ratna Ivone Mandang²**

¹Accounting Department,
State Polytechnic of Manado, Indonesia

²Business Administration Department,
State Polytechnic of Manado, Indonesia

Abstract:

This research is using a quantitative approach with experiment methods called “non-equivalent control group design”. The purpose of this research is to find out how effective is Task Based Language Teaching (TBLT) compare to the Convention one, applied in Politeknik Negeri Manado for English Teaching Process. The experiment is applied to 2 groups of students at Semester 2 from Accounting Department; class II C and class II B. The role of each group is different according to that experiment method, one group is for Experiment and the other is for Control. The main sample data of the group goes to the class II C as the Experiment group and TBLT is applied in this class. From the linguistics’ point of view it is shown that during first to third meeting, the experiment group who are working with Task Based achieved higher percentage compare to the Control Group. By assessing those facts, we can prove that TBLT as experiment and methods given to the experiment group is a better treatment to train students to do their activities to develop their abilities in learning English. The speaking abilities are assessed by the topic: “Describing City” to each class and the higher ability of speaking goes to the experiment group. So, we can also conclude that there is differences performance achieved by those two groups: the experiment with TBLT is more creative! in speaking skills compare to the one using conventional approach. The both aspects language skills as learning outcomes are linguistic abilities and speaking skills are shown by the result of posttest, at the end of this research period.

Keywords: task based language teaching, effective, performance, learning outcomes

English language as one of the foreign language which takes a place as the highest rank of foreign languages in terms of use in any occasion and circumstance and it is widely known as the international language, has not being used maximally in the Indonesian context. This condition is due to various factors. One of the factors is the teaching method used by the instructor of teacher. Learning method employed by the instructor or teacher determines the learning style of the students in the classroom. In fact, learning teaching of language learning, particularly English, only emphasizes on selective elements. Since the learning method employed is monotonous, students are not interested with English learning. Students tend to be passive during the learning. Thus, it is urgent and essential to discover and employ a learning process alternative to encourage the passion of students in learning English.

Current method employed by language instructor or teacher is insufficient to deal with the existing challenge regarding the student need. It requires an alternative method to support the accomplishment of learning objective. In addition, according to the observation, by directing students in submitting the assignments, both individual and group assignments, with various methods which focus on the students or student-centered learning, students are more encouraged to perform language learning which focuses on the speaking skill. In fact, students' interest in learning is still low. The low interest of learning is indicated by having insignificant learning outcomes, particularly in terms of communication ability of English. With regard to this issue, alternative learning method is required to be designed to promote and encourage students' interest on the material presented. In addition, the alternative learning method is expected able to foster the ability of the students regarding the material as well as encouraging the active participation of students in the learning process which generates a student-centered learning. One alternative method which is possible to encourage active participation of student is task based language teaching or TBLT.

The major factor of the aforementioned problems is the insufficient effort of the lecturer or instructor in implementing learning method or technique during English course to promote conducive environment of learning. In addition, the supporting facility of English course is still inadequate which is contributing to the depressed level of students' interest in learning English and as a result, the learning outcome is also low. To answer the following issue, thus, it requires a further study regarding the effectiveness of Task Based Language Teaching (TBLT) in English Course.

Task based learning method is a learning method which employs assignment or project to encourage and attract the interest of learner or student during the learning process

which at the end it could improve the ability of student in terms of speaking ability. In addition, this method also serves as a method to accomplish the language learning objective through communicative approach. The effectiveness of Task-based language teaching method can only see the improvement of students' learning outcomes during spoken activity. Task based language teaching is the second language teaching approach which focuses on the assignment or project to the students.

The primary characteristic of task based language teaching is the authenticity of method which means that the assignments or projects given by teacher to students are related to the real life of student; in addition, it aims at preparing students to focus on the language learning process instead of the language knowledge itself and allowing students to use experience context they possess as the essential element which supports learning process in the classroom. In general, any assignment and project given to the students can be defined as task based language teaching method. However, what makes task based language teaching method is different from the conventional method is the assignment given to the students in the initial meeting of the learning. According to the experience encountered by the instructor or teacher, the moment the students are given a new assignment or project, instructor or teacher will elaborate more the material to deliver certain concept of language to the students. However, within task based language teaching, students are demanded to be able to understand initially the material and the conceptual delivery by the instructor or teacher will be limited to the assessment of right or wrong, or even only an evaluation.

By employing task based language teaching method, the role of lecturer, instructor or teacher will be optimized. According to the available alternative to resolve the learning issue and improve the ability of students in terms of speaking skill, task based activity is one of the method which is able to improve the skill. Task based activity is a technique or method of speaking skill teaching which is developed from communicative approach focusing on the role of assignment or project to accomplish the communication goal within spoken communication activity.

Task based activity aims at facilitating students to encourage a meaningful communication and interaction. In the implementation of task based activity, the learners will engage on the activity which is related with meaning negotiating, paraphrasing, and performing experiment which leads them into a successful language acquisition (Richard and Renandya, 2002:94). These activities are in line with the definition of task proposed by Skehan which defines that task is an activity; in terms of meaning, it is an essential element, which comprises of communication issue to be solved and closely related to the daily activities. The principles of task based language teaching are also in line with innovative learning concept which is currently promoted in the educational setting.

Task gives learners some very interesting advantages to be taken into account (Beglar and Hunt, 2002). *Task* provides *input* and opportunities for learners to use language that is meaningful, that is of course regarded as essential for mastery of the language, especially spoken communication ability. In addition, the *task* provides linguistically rich environments which are basically able to provide learners with language skills. *Task* gives a lot of emphasis on providing opportunities to generate force language learners to give more attention to the shape and the interrelationship between form and meaning. Finally, the relationship between form and function is more easily understood in *the task-based learning activity*.

In accordance with the aforementioned, the researchers are interested to conduct a research to analyze the effectiveness of Task Based Language Teaching in English Language Course State Polytechnic of Manado in 2012/2013.

2. Method

The research was conducted from May and June 2014 in State Polytechnic of Manado. This study employed two classes, experiments class using *Task-Based Language Teaching* and control class with conventional methods. The data source in this research is the implementation learning with *Task-Based Language Teaching* from several aspects of language skills and the learning outcomes. The sampling technique used in this study was a *cluster random sampling*. In this study, the data collection was done by employing test, distributing questionnaire, and observation. The research instrument used was a written test at the beginning of the implementation, questionnaires, and observation. For the purposes of checking the validity of data, in this study was conducted validity and reliability test. The analysis in this study using pre-requisite test analysis, namely normality and homogeneity test to test the hypothesis using the t-test.

3. Findings and Discussion

Before the lecturer explains a material about describing city, students of experiment and control class were asked to do a pre-test in order to identify the initial ability. The pre-test performed consisted of written test and questionnaires. The results of pre-test of both experiment and control class is presented in the following Table 1. The results of pre-test obtained 64 as the highest score and 35 as the lowest score. Thus, the average of the pre-test score is 49.52 and the standard deviation is 6.50.

Table 1: The Data Frequency Distribution of Control Group Pre-test

No	Score	Absolute Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	35 - 39	1	4
2	40 - 44	3	14
3	45 - 49	6	29
4	50 - 54	7	33
5	55 - 59	3	14
6	60 - 64	1	5
Total		21	100

Furthermore, based on the data in Table 1, it can be seen that the score of the control group pretest above average as much as 52% and 48% were below average.

Based on the data obtained, the results of the posttest control group obtained 84 as the highest value and the lowest score of 55. Based on these data, the average score was 70.14 and standard deviation is 6.54.

Table 2: The Data Frequency Distribution of Control Group Posttest

No	Score	Absolute Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	55 - 59	1	5
2	60 - 64	3	14
3	65 - 69	7	33
4	70 - 74	6	29
5	75 - 79	2	10
6	80 - 84	2	10
Total		21	100

Furthermore, based on the data in Table 2, it can be seen that the posttest score of the control group is above average as much as 49% and 51% were below average.

Based on the data obtained, the pretest results of experiment group obtained 68 as the highest score and the lowest score of 39. Based on these data, the average score was 53.04 and standard deviation is 7.05.

Table 3: The Data Frequency Distribution of Experiment Group Pretest

No	Score	Absolute Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	39 - 43	1	4
2	44 - 48	4	17
3	49 - 53	7	30
4	54 - 58	7	30
5	59 - 63	3	13
6	64 - 68	1	4
Total		23	100

Furthermore, based on the data in Table 3, it can be seen that the pretest score of the experiment group is above average as much as 47% and 53% were below average.

Based on the data obtained, the posttest results of experiment group obtained 98 as the highest score and the lowest score of 63. Based on these data, the average score was 81.47 and standard deviation is 8.90.

Table 4: The Data Frequency Distribution of Experiment Group Posttest

No	Score	Absolute Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	63 - 68	2	5
2	69 - 74	4	14
3	75 - 80	5	33
4	81 - 86	7	29
5	87 - 92	3	10
6	93 - 98	3	10
Total		23	100

Based on the data in Table 4, it can be seen that the value of the Experiments group posttest is 49% above the average and 51% below average.

After conducting a pretest, each class were given a treatment, experiment class with Task Based Language Teaching and Control Class with conventional method in English Course. As for the posttest, it is in the form of written test, questionnaires, and observation.

The posttest results of experiment and control class are presented in Table 4. Before performing hypothesis testing, prerequisite analysis testing were conducted; normality and homogeneity testing. This testing were performed to determine whether sample is normally distributed and from homogen population. Before performing t-test, it is necessary to perform variant normality and homogeneity testing. The results of normality and homogeneity testing were presented in the following explanation.

a. Normality testing

Liliefors testing was employed in the normality testing to determine whether the data used is normal or not on the 5% significance rate. The data distribution is considered normal if χ^2 (Chikuadrat) count < χ^2 (Chikuadrat) dari table.

The result of normality testing is presented in the following Table 5:

Table 5: Liliefors Testing for Normality Testing

Experiment class	χ^2 count	χ^2 table $\alpha = 0.05$	Conclusion
Posttest	2,91	7,81	Normal
Control class			
Posttest	2,7	7,81	Normal

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the chi squared value is calculated in both groups smaller than chi squared value obtained from the table. This shows the data has normal distribution.

b. Varians Homogeneity Testing

Homogeneity testing is used to determine whether the two sets of data to be analyzed from the population is homogeneous or not. Bartlett test was used in testing homogeneity. The data can be considered meet the assumption of homogeneity or derived populations have homogenous variant if the value of χ^2 (chisquared) $hi\ tung < \chi^2$ (Chisquared) of table.

Table 6: Bartlett Testing for Varians Homogeneity testing

Class	Chisquared count	Chisquared table $\alpha = 0.05$	Conclusion
Pretest	1.93	3.84	Homogenous
Posttest	0.13	3.84	Homogenous

According to Table 6, chisquared count of pretest and posttest is smaller than chisquared table. It affirms that the data obtained within this research meet the requirements of homogeneity or the data obtained from homogeny variant group. The primary data of this research indicates that the average pretest score of experiment class is 60.769 while pretest score of control group is 60.625.

The result of hypothesis testing indicates that the both samples are equal. In addition, the average posttest score of experiment class is 76.635 and control class is 71.562. From the data obtained, it can be seen that the experiment class improvement was 15.866 meanwhile the improvement of control class is 10.937. From the t-test analysis, it obtained the t count 3.211 is greater than t table 1.67. Thus, it can be stated that the language aspects of experiment class is higher than control class.

This finding is due to the ability of student within Task Based Language Teaching is higher than students in control class with conventional method. In IIC Class, there is a student who is able to perform as assistant which takes a role in assisting the other students who are lacking in the learning. Task Based Language Teaching could motivate the students more in improving the creativity which allows the communication ability.

The benefit of Task Based Language Teaching are 1) task is an activity performed as a response of language understanding. For instance, drawing a map along with listening to a recorder. The employment of various tasks in language teaching aims at encouraging a communicative learning. 2) Task is an activity performed by students to obtain information understanding from learning process and enables teacher to control and manage the process.

3) Task is an activity which emphasizes a) the meaning, b) the communication issue to be solved, c) the relationship of real world activity comparison. By employing Task Based Language Teaching, students could obtain a maximum understanding of the material as well as improving the language skills and communication ability.

For the aspects of language learning outcomes of students, the average value for the experiment class pretest was 81.00 and in the control group was 81.25. For the average post-test score is the experimental class and the control class 96.78 is 93.28. Of the average value Prete and posttest above, the difference between the value of pretest and posttest in the experimental class is 19.38, while for the control class is 1 to 5.62. From the result of t test analysis, the value of $t = 1.725$ is greater than $t_{table} = 1.67$, so it can be concluded that affective aspects of learning outcomes for the students in the experimental class is higher than the control class.

In addition, for students conducting direct task will certainly be easier to understand and is able to perform a given task learning. For student learning outcomes, the average value of the results of the experimental class is 2,64 and the control class is 2.36. From the result of t test analysis, the value of $t = 2.06$ is greater than $t_{table} = 1.67$, so it can be inferred results for aspects of language learning is most students in the experimental class is higher than the control class.

4. Conclusion and Suggestions

According to the literature review and the data analysis of this study, it can be concluded that the method of learning with *task-based language teaching* can improve the learning outcomes of students majoring in accounting State Polytechnic of Manado.

In addition, it is important for the English teacher or lecturer to teach using task based language teaching, particularly in improving the language skills of students rather than using conventional method. These research findings could be as a reference for the future researchers to conduct a further research in obtaining additional knowledge and information regarding task based language teaching in order to develop the learning within higher education.

Acknowledgement

The researchers would like to deliver the greatest gratitude to the Ministry of Education and Culture for granting a researcher fund for this present study through Higher Education Operational Funding (BONPTN) 2013.

References

1. Azies, F., dan Alwasilah C., A. *Pengajaran bahasa Komunikatif; Teori dan Praktek*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya, 1996
2. Brown, Douglas H. *Prinsip Pembelajaran dan Pengajaran Bahasa*. Pearson Education. Terjemahan Noor Cholis & Yusi A. Pareanom. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 2007.
3. Brown, G. and G. Yule. *Teaching the Spoken Language*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1983.
4. Ellis R. *Task-based Language Teaching and Learning*. Oxford, OUP 2003.
5. Gagne M., Robert and Leslie J. Briggs. *Principles of Instructional Design*. New York: Halt, Renhart and Winston, 1974
6. Krashen, S. *The Natural Approach: Language Acquisition in the Classroom*. Prentice Hall, 1996.
7. Kris van Den Branden, Martin Bygate, John Norris. *Task-Based Language Teaching, A Reader*. Philadelphia, John Benjamins Publishing Comp, 2009.
8. Leaver B. L. & J. Willis, (eds) *Task-based Instruction in ForeignLanguage Education: practices and programs*. Washington DC, 2004.
9. Long, M. *A role for instruction in second language acquisition: task-based language teaching*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters, 1985.
10. Metler, A. Craig. *Action Research: Teachers as Researchers in the Classroom*. London. Sage Pub, 2009.
11. Nunan, David. *Practical English Language Teaching*. NY: McGraw-Hill, 2003.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). and European Journal of Literature, Language and Linguistics Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).